

Social Media Approaches on BIM Collaboration

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Abstract

Construction sector is known to be very fragmented. Project teams contain diverse professions who must collaborate and communicate, but often lack the will, the skills, or the tools to do so. In other areas of collaboration social media plays an important role because it is providing for informal communication which people are more comfortable with. As a result, the general use of social media has increased during the last decade. From this background, this thesis aims to answer two questions: (1) What is the impact of social media on BIM (building information modelling) collaboration and (2), how is it supporting this collaboration. To answer these questions, a literature review is conducted for choosing and discussing studies related to social media and BIM collaboration. Findings show that social media increases communication between team members by sharing images, ideas, and work progress updates. Moreover, it creates a community of BIM experts and of professionals who are sharing the same concerns for the success of the project. The informal knowledge and information exchange enabled by social media technology provides better understanding of project requirements, helps to project managers to improve the management because they can understand better the skills and needs of the team members. Overall, supporting the BIM collaboration with social media tools improves project collaboration. Future work should study how to make BIM tools more social or how to make generic social tools work better with BIM data.

Dissertation:

Link for full text

Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/gICjJamo-t8>

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